

Hematopoietic stem and progenitor cells in 3D *ex vivo* culture

Stem cell biology

Smaller size and rounded morphology

Reduced DNA damage and DNA damage response

Metabolic remodeling

Reduced oxidative stress

Decreased p38 MAPK activation

Polarized tubulin architecture

3D vs. 2D in gene therapy applications

Comparable genetic engineering

CRISPR/Cas9
± AAV6

Prime editing

Base editing

Lentiviral gene
addition

Improved engraftment
and clonal output

